

Performance Evaluation of Fractional Frequency Reuse in Multi-Beam Satellite System

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Abstract—The ever-growing demand for communication services poses significant challenges in efficiently utilizing the limited spectrum resources, particularly in non-terrestrial networks (NTN). One major challenge in broadband satellite communication is inter-beam interference, appears when a certain frequency bin is reused among the coverage area. In essence, this results in complications to meet the quality of service (QoS) requirements. Fractional Frequency Reuse (FFR) has been widely adopted in traditional terrestrial networks (TN) to address such challenges but not been extensively explored in NTN due to constraints posed by legacy satellite payloads constructed by array fed reflectors. In the forthcoming broadband satellite missions, direct radiating arrays (DRA) will enable a flexible operation of the beams, allowing irregular deployments and mimicking the FFR schemes. This advancements provides an opportunity to dynamically adjust the inner to outer beam radius ratios (IOR), enabling the application of FFR principles in NTN. By this perspective, this paper extends the FFR paradigm into multi-beam satellite system under uniform user traffic conditions. Specifically, this paper investigates two FFR strategies within NTN, namely Strict FFR (S-FFR) and introducing a novel technique coined as Partially Strict FFR (PS-FFR) and conducts the evaluation across varying IOS and bandwidth distributions. The performance analysis indicates that PS-FFR outperforms the Strict FFR in terms of overall system capacity while both show a performance gain against so-called Frequency Reuse-4.

Index Terms—Fractional Frequency Reuse, Non-Terrestrial Networks, Inter-beam Interference

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of non-terrestrial networks (NTN), the multi-beam satellite system emerges as a powerful paradigm due to its profound ability to generate focused beams. This enables high capacity and efficient resource utilization ensuring the quality-of-service (QoS). However, a significant challenge hinders its full potential due to the presence of inter-beam interference. This impairment particularly appears when the users in multiple beams utilize the same frequency bands which ultimately impacts the overall system capacity.

To cope with the analogous problem in terrestrial networks (TN), frequency reuse (FR) schemes are widely adopted where different cells utilize different frequency bands to mitigate the co-channel interference and found as profound solutions to enhance the system performance. In light of this achievement, it is worthy for space industry and academia to scout TN technological advances so that they can be eventually incor-

porated in the NTN domain. This is the case of the original fractional frequency reuse (FFR). In contrast to FR, FFR works on concentric cell layouts so that terminals closer to the base station operate in a different spectrum chunk compared to the ones at the edge of the cell. In satellite systems, one may opt to consider concentric beams which can now be deployed by recent adoption of hybrid analog digital beam-forming solutions at the payload.

To this end in literature, the comparisons among different FFR schemes in the cellular scenario are performed in [1] and [2]. The former studied performance of the Strict and Soft FFR in OFDMA system for uniformly distributed users, while the latter one studied the FFR schemes comparison in hotspot scenario and applied artificial intelligence (AI) enabled algorithm to further improve the system performance.

However, mapping those traditional FFR techniques in the paradigm of multi-beam satellite systems have different implications. Considering this, a couple of studies about FFR schemes in multi-beam satellite can be found in [3] and [4]. The former work focused on deriving the theoretical formulation of uplink interference and then comparing the different FFR schemes to analyze the performance while the later one initially reviewed the FFR based static, semi-static and dynamic ICIC techniques and then proposes a scheduling-based algorithm in frequency domain to maximize the minimum carrier to interference (C/I) ratio. A brief study in [5] depicts just an idea of dynamically choosing reuse factor depending on beams density to improve spectrum resources.

Amongst these works, due to legacy array fed reflector monolithic beam creation in broadband systems, it is merely a discussion on the impact of inner beam and outer beam radius relation on signal to interference and noise ratio (SINR) for downlink scenario. Since now with the advancement in the DBF, it is possible to employ variable inner and outer beamwidths. Taking this into account, this paper provides following contribution in the framework of S- FFR and PS- FFR in multi-beam satellite system. It first contributes in studying the interrelation of inner and outer beamwidth in FFR and identify the ratio that maximizes the overall throughput especially when the users are uniformly distributed in each beam. Second, it introduces PS-FFR that allocates frequency resources with reuse factor (FR) of 4 to the beam edge

users and allows the users closer to beam center to reuse the frequency from one of the adjacent beam edges. This identifies in improving the overall capacity. Moreover, the outcomes also provide insights on performance by using different bandwidth distributions for S-FFR and PS-FFR.

Considering the problem herein, this paper is organized as follows. Section II models the framework of multi-beam satellite system explicitly focuses on deriving the relations of essential KPIs to analyze the system performance. Section III instigates the discussion on S-FFR and introduces PS-FFR framework. The problem framework and the relevant system constraints are formulate in same Section. Section IV provides the deep insights into simulation framework and comprehensive discussion on the outcomes. Finally, the conclusion is drawn in Section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Multi-Beam Satellite System

Before indulging into FFR discussion, it is vital to comprehend the multi-beam satellite system and the model which is essential. For this purpose, consider a multi-beam satellite system with K beams where each beam k , $k = 1, \dots, K$ is serving N fixed uniformly distributed users where $n = 1, \dots, N$. In this way, the user n located in desired beam denoted as beam $k(n)$. Each beam k is allocated with B_w bandwidth resources while the transmission power resources to beam k is P_k . Hence, the received signal r_n at the user n in k_{th} beam can be represented as [6],

$$r_n = \mathbf{h}_n^H \mathbf{s} \quad (1)$$

where H is Hermitian transpose, \mathbf{s} is the transmitted signal defined as $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{x}$, where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ are transmitted symbols and $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times N}$ the beamforming matrix, $\mathbf{h}_n \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ is the channel vector associated with particular user n . Concatenating all the channel vectors, the above channel state information (CSI) parameter can be rewritten as,

$$\mathbf{r}_n = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times K}$ now represents the system channel matrix. For better understanding, the channel matrix \mathbf{H} is further split as $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{B}$, where the real matrix \mathbf{B} determines by the satellite antenna radiation pattern, transmission gain, receiver antenna gain, free space path loss and the noise power while \mathbf{D} represents the phase-slant due to different propagation path between the users. Considering this, any (n, k) entry of the matrix \mathbf{H} can be given as,

$$h_{n,k} = \frac{\sqrt{G_{t(n,k)} G_{r(n,k)} G_{tx(n,k)}}}{(4\pi \frac{d_{nk}}{\lambda}) \sqrt{\kappa B_w}} \quad (3)$$

where $G_{t(n,k)}$ and $G_{r(n,k)}$ represent the transmission gain and receiving gain to n_{th} user in beam k respectively while $G_{tx(n,k)}$ is the gain defined by transmission radiation pattern at the n_{th} user location, d_{nk} is the distance between satellite antenna k and the user n , λ is the wavelength and κ is

Fig. 1: A subset of Multi-beam satellite system with universal Strict FFR scheme

Boltzmann constant. if the user n is located in desired beam $k(n)$ then $g_{(n,k(n))} = |h_{n,k(n)}|^2$ represents the channel gain that user is experienced in desired beam. The users in adjacent beams may utilize the common frequency bands, therefore, the signal received by any user should also include the interference caused by the other users using the same frequency sub-bands in other beams. Hence, the SINR for the user n in its desired beam $k(n)$ can be formulated as.

$$SINR_{n,k(n)} = \frac{P_{k(n)} g_{(n,k(n))}}{\sum_{k=1, k \neq k(n)}^K P_{(n,k)} g_{(n,k)} + N_o} \quad (4)$$

where $P_{k(n)}$ and $P_{(n,k)}$ is transmitting power allocated to desired beam and all other interfering co-frequency beams, respectively and N_o is white Gaussian noise.

B. Offered Throughput

Following the SINR relation formulated in (4), the average offered capacity per beam considering a uniform user scheduling in time is,

$$C_k = \frac{1}{|T_k|} \left(\sum_{n \in T_k} B_w \log_2(1 + SINR_{n,k(n)}) \right) \quad (5)$$

where $|T_k|$ is the cardinality of a set T_k which provides the total number of users being served in desired beam. The total average offered system capacity can be given as,

$$C_{tot} = \sum_{k=1}^K C_k \quad (6)$$

III. FRACTIONAL FREQUENCY REUSE

As indicated in Section II, the users in multiple beams utilizing same frequency sub-bands prone to inter-beam interference. To this end, it envisaged that FFR techniques can

be utilized to minimize this impact. Typically in FFR, each satellite beam is divided into two areas, Inner Beam Area (IBA) and Outer Beam Area (OBA) and the users in both areas serve with distinct frequency resources. In this realm, this paper introduces and maps PS-FFR scheme to multi-beam satellite system and study along with traditional Strict FFR.

A. Strict FFR

Fig. 1 illustrates a subset of multi-beam satellite system exerting typical S-FFR scheme. In S-FFR, the IBA utilizes FR of 1 meaning that the users in IBA of each beam assign with the common frequency sub-band. Meanwhile the FR of 4 is utilized for OBA which allows the users in each adjacent 4 beams utilize the disjoint frequency sub-bands. This stringent requirement needs to be in place since the SINR in OBA is more prone to co-channel interference than IBA. This disjoint sub-bands make OBA resilient to co-channel interference. Due to this, S-FFR requires in total FR $4 + 1$.

Further interpreting Fig. 1, α is an azimuth angle of a desired user terminal relative to the beam center (BC) of desired beam for calculating the relative beam gain while β is an azimuth angle of interfering user terminal relative to the desired BC. This angle provides the relative beam gain from interfering user to desired BC as used in (3) and (4). In S-FFR, the SINR relation will be partitioned into SINR corresponding to IBA and OBA users. Assuming that the transmit power is same for both areas, the SINR relation for S-FFR is reformulated, where i and j are the users belong to IBA and OBA, respectively.

$$\text{SINR}_{n,k(n)}^{\text{S-FFR}} = \begin{cases} \text{SINR}_{i,k(i)}^{\text{inner}} = \frac{P g_{(i,k(i))}^{\text{inner}}}{\sum_{k=1, k \neq k(i)}^K P g_{(i,k)}^{\text{inner}} + N_o} \\ \text{SINR}_{j,k(j)}^{\text{outer}} = \frac{P g_{(j,k(j))}^{\text{outer}}}{\sum_{k=1, k \neq k(j)}^K P g_{(j,k)}^{\text{outer}} + N_o} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

B. Partially Strict FFR

Analogous to S-FFR, PS-FFR utilizes the FR 4 in OBA but it does not exert FR 1 in IBA as is the case in S-FFR. Moreover, unlike Soft Frequency Reuse (SFR) that although utilizes the entire bandwidth by reusing all adjacent OBA frequencies in IBA, resulting more interference cases both in OBA and IBA [4]. Instead PS-FFR offers the IBA users to utilize the sub-bands similar to one of the adjacent OBA users. This allows the utilization of bandwidth more aggressively than S-FFR since it requires to split the total bandwidth per beam into 4 frequency sub-bands rather than $4 + 1$. In case of PS-FFR, the SINR relation is reformulated for IBA and OBA as below,

$$\text{SINR}_{n,k(n)}^{\text{PS-FFR}} = \begin{cases} \text{SINR}_{i,k(i)}^{\text{inner}} = \frac{P g_{(i,k(i))}^{\text{inner}}}{\sum_{k=1, k \neq k(i)}^K P g_{(i,k)}^{\text{inner}} + P g_{(j,k)}^{\text{outer}} + N_o} \\ \text{SINR}_{j,k(j)}^{\text{outer}} = \frac{P g_{(j,k(j))}^{\text{outer}}}{\sum_{k=1, k \neq k(j)}^K P g_{(j,k)}^{\text{outer}} + P g_{(i,k)}^{\text{inner}} + N_o} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The offered throughput provided in (5) can be reformulated for both S-FFR and PS-FFR by replacing the B_w by B_w^{inner} and B_w^{output} and SINR expressions derived in (7) and (8), respectively. The total average system throughput now can be written as,

$$C_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{k=1}^K (C_k^{\text{inner}} + C_k^{\text{outer}}) \quad (9)$$

Now with the goal of maximizing the system capacity, the significance of IOR is critical since it classifies the users in IBA and OBA, thereby determining if they would share the common sub-bands or utilize the distinct frequency resources. Moreover, the system capacity is an explicit function of available bandwidth and it is evident that the total bandwidth can not be fully utilized in each beam due to reuse factor in both S-FFR and PS-FFR. Considering these constraints, the capacity maximization problem can be formulated as,

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\text{IOR}}{\text{maximize}} && \sum_{k=1}^K (C_k^{\text{inner}} + C_k^{\text{outer}}) \\ & \text{subject to} && c_1 : 0 < \text{IB}^\circ < \text{OB}^\circ \\ & && c_2^{\text{S-FFR}} : B_w^{\text{inner}} + B_w^{\text{outer}} \leq 2 \frac{B_w}{4+1} \\ & && c_3^{\text{PS-FFR}} : B_w^{\text{inner}} + B_w^{\text{outer}} \leq 2 \frac{B_w}{4} \end{aligned}$$

In this problem, the search variable is IOR. Constraints c_1 represents two conditions: 1) IBA must be greater than 0 and 2) IB (inner beamwidth) must less than OB (outer beamwidth). Failing to fulfill condition 1 leads to represent full FR system with FR 4 while not satisfying condition 2 results in no FR system and thereby, all beams will occupy same frequency resources. $c_2^{\text{S-FFR}}$ dedicates to S-FFR where the total bandwidth resources per beam partitioned into 5 sub-bandwidths since IBA entitled to use FR 1 and OBA sets to use FR 4. Therefore, out of 5 sub-bands, only one sub-band can be allocated to each IBA and OBA per beam. $c_3^{\text{PS-FFR}}$ depicts the same situation for PS-FFR as given in S-FFR instead the total bandwidth resources per beam split into 4. This is due to the fact, IBA is not occupying the disjoint frequency resources but utilizing the same resources from one of the adjacent OBA.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section comprises on two sections where the first part inclusively defines the overall simulation environment given the system parameters and the second part comprehends the performance based on defined simulated FFR framework.

A. Simulation Framework

The defined FFR model is applied over a subset of 7 beams extracted from 230 beam pattern covering the European region as shown in Figure 2, where each beam is modeled with function as in [7]. In this framework, at first, the uniform distributed users are simulated within the defined outer beam boundary from BC and then classified them as IBA and OBA

Fig. 2: A subset of 7 beams extracted from 230 beam pattern over the European region

users. To correctly classifying the users, the haversine distance metric is used over SINR since SINR is not reliable metric for user classification in satellite system due to low margin between BC to 3dB beamwidth, just a minor impairment leads to misclassify the users. [8]. The pseudo-code of algorithm to classify the IBA and OBA users is as follows,

1 Classification of IBA and OBA Users

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1: Initialize two sets:  $U_{inner}, U_{outer} = \{n = 1, \dots, N\}$ 
2: for user  $n$  in any beam  $k$  do
3:   if  $d_{(n,BC)} \leq \gamma_{inner}$  then
4:      $U_{inner} \leftarrow n$ 
5:      $U_{outer} \leftarrow 0$ .
6:   else
7:      $U_{outer} \leftarrow n$ 
8:      $U_{inner} \leftarrow 0$ 
9:   end if
10: end for

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where $d_{(n,BC)}$ is haversine distance in km from BC to user n , γ_{inner} is a distance based threshold in km calculated from BC to defined inner beam boundary, U_{inner} and U_{outer} representing a set of classified IBA and OBA users, respectively. Once the users are allocated to IBA and OBA $\forall k$ beams then the frequency resources, power and bandwidth allocation is performed. Subsequently, SINR and throughput is calculated using (7), (8) and (9). The simulation parameters are given in Table I. It is important to remark that the relation between beam gain and radius have been obtained considering a modeling of a horn antenna. Beam radius is defined at half-beamwidth. It is left for further work about how to implement this beam in an hybrid digital-analog solution.

B. Performance Evaluation

After defining the paramount simulation environment, this subsection imparts the evaluation of defined FFR techniques and explicitly compares their performances. Since the goal is to identify the optimal IOR through search that maximizes the overall system throughput C_{tot} , Fig. 3 and 4 shows the results of Monte Carlo simulation depicting the S-FFR and PS-FFR

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Parameters	Values
Operating Frequency	20 GHz
Total Bandwidth	2 GHz
Transmit Power	15dBW
Receiver G/T	17 dB.K ⁻¹
Number of Beams (K)	7
User Distribution	Uniform
Users Per Beam (N)	5
Outer Beamwidth (OB)	0.32°
Inner Beamwidth (IB)	0.01° – 0.31°
Monte Carlo Trails	4000

throughput performance as a function of IORs, respectively while taking FR-4 as benchmark. Moreover, the impact of bandwidth distribution on throughput is worth to study where each curve is shown as different bandwidth distribution. Three cases are distinguished to analyze the performance, in essence, when same bandwidths are allocated to both outer and inner beams, when the bandwidth allocated to inner beam B_w^{inner} is 4 times the B_w^{outer} and vice-versa. Note that the sum of B_w^{inner} and B_w^{outer} must satisfy both constraints c_2^{S-FFR} and c_3^{PS-FFR} .

Fig. 3: Total system throughput C_{tot} as a function of IOR and different bandwidth distributions for S-FFR framework.

The interpretation of Fig. 3 and 4 can be performed by dividing into three regions. On the one hand, the first region is critical region where the C_{tot} achieves the maximum value, is at when IOR equals to 0.68 and allocated B_w^{inner} is 4 times more than the B_w^{outer} for both S-FFR and PS-FFR. The second region is instantly after the critical region when the curves start gradually decreasing and approach near or below the benchmark. It is the fact as IOR approaches to 1, S-FFR leads towards the Full FR i.e. FR 1 where all the beams would utilize common frequency resources since IBA would be fully occupied the entire beam region. Similarly, it becomes FR 4 for PS-FFR where 4 adjacent beams would use distinct frequency resources. The third region is before the critical region when IOR with lower values. The average C_{tot} over

Fig. 4: Total system throughput C_{tot} as a function of IOR and different bandwidth distributions for PS-FFR framework.

this region is lower since the inner region is contracted and many times it leads to the case when there would not any users in IBA. Therefore, the offered capacity is predominantly associated to only OBA users. It is evident, for instance for low IOR values, when B_w^{inner} is 4 times more than B_w^{outer} , only B_w^{outer} would contribute in C_{tot} . On the contrary, when B_w^{outer} is dominating for lower IOR, the C_{tot} will be higher as expected.

Interestingly, the C_{tot} in PS-FFR is reported to be outperformed the S-FFR paradigm especially at critical region. Because and since S-FFR scheme assigns IBA with the common frequency resources in all beams and IBA is nearly halved the OBA at this point, therefore, it will experience stronger gain focused inside IBA. This, in result, suffers with higher interference as well from the other beams that are using common frequency resources. On the contrary, IBA of each beam in PS-FFR utilizes frequency resources from one of the OBA regions of other beam and this minimizes the impact of interference in the inner beams which results in improving the overall system capacity and can be seen by comparing the empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) in Figure 5.

V. CONCLUSION

Taking the benefit of DRA capabilities of enabling the flexible beams operation, this paper explores the FFR in NTN. In essence, it seizes the opportunity of dynamically adjusting the inner beamwidth to identify the optimal IOR where maximum system capacity could be achieved for uniform user distribution. Moreover, it introduces the PS-FFR scheme to better utilize the spectrum resources along with maximizing the overall system capacity in comparison with Strict FFR. The analysis demonstrates that PS-FFR offers superior overall system capacity than S-FFR and the so-called FR-4 scheme. Subsequently, the outcomes achieved herein provide the insights to extend the work into more complex environment of non-uniform user traffic scenarios and investigate dynamic IOR adjustments based on real-time traffic patterns.

Fig. 5: The CDF comparison of S-FFR and PS-FFR for both IBA and OBA

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